

Review

Phytopharmacology and Fertility – The Traditional Chinese Medicine Perspective, Formulas, and Scientific Evidence.

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Abstract

Infertility is a significant global health problem, requiring comprehensive therapeutic approaches. Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) offers a traditional medical system that has been used for thousands of years to treat infertility. This study aims to explore the TCM perspective on infertility and presents a review of the scientific evidence regarding the application of Chinese herbal medicine in this area.

To this end, a review of the scientific literature is conducted, including randomised clinical trials, meta-analyses, and other relevant studies on the application of Chinese herbal medicine in infertility. An analysis of the available information on the TCM perspective on infertility is also carried out, including the patterns of disharmony (syndromes) associated with this condition.

The results indicate that TCM offers a holistic and personalised approach to the treatment of infertility, based on the identification of patterns of disharmony and the application of therapeutic techniques such as herbal medicine. Furthermore, the scientific literature reveals that several Chinese herbal formulas demonstrate positive effects on improving semen quality, sperm motility, pregnancy rates, and other parameters relevant to fertility. The mechanisms of action of these formulas are complex, involving the modulation of signalling pathways, hormonal regulation, improvement of endometrial receptivity, protection against oxidative stress, and other biological processes.

It can be concluded that Chinese herbal medicine presents itself as a promising tool in the treatment of infertility, offering a complementary and potentiating approach to conventional treatments. The integration of TCM in reproductive health care can improve clinical outcomes and the well-being of patients facing infertility.

Keywords: Fertility; Infertility; Chinese Herbal Medicine; Traditional Chinese Medicine.

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1. Introduction

Reproduction is a complex biological process that enables living beings to generate offspring, ensuring the continuation of the species. Fertility, the ability to accomplish this process, depends on the intricate interaction of the reproductive system in males and females, shaping their distinct characteristics and behaviours ¹.

The inability to conceive after one year or more of regular, unprotected sexual intercourse is defined as infertility ²⁻⁴. This common reproductive health condition can affect both men and women. Approximately one in six couples worldwide experiences infertility at some point in life ⁵, which may have a significant impact on the emotional and social well-being of those affected ⁶⁻⁹.

However, infertility not only affects individuals and families but also society. Declining fertility is linked to population ageing and to complex social and economic challenges¹⁰.

Addressing this condition is a complex problem that requires comprehensive solutions, including improved access to fertility treatments, raising public awareness about infertility, and supporting those who face this challenge. An effective approach may reduce the negative effects of infertility on individuals, families, and society¹¹.

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TCM offers a holistic approach to health, seeking a harmonious balance of internal biological functions, and emerges as a potential therapeutic option¹³.

According to recent scientific literature, this traditional medical system has been increasingly investigated¹⁴⁻²⁶, alongside efforts to build bridges between TCM and Western medicine²⁷⁻³⁵.

Several TCM techniques have already demonstrated promising results for enhancing fertility^{12,36-40}. Chinese herbal medicine, also referred to as Chinese phytopharmacology or Chinese herbal therapy⁴¹, is one such technique.

This study aims to contextualise fertility and infertility, describe the TCM perspective on these conditions, and review scientific evidence regarding the application of Chinese herbal medicine in fertility care.

2. Infertility

2.1. Female Infertility

Female infertility can have various causes, such as problems in the menstrual cycle, endometriosis (when uterine tissue grows outside the uterus), pelvic adhesions (scar tissue that interferes with organ function), difficulties with ovulation, tubal obstructions (which prevent the egg from travelling from the ovary to the uterus), hyperprolactinemia, and other uterine abnormalities^{10,42}.

Conventional approaches may include fertility drugs, surgery, in vitro fertilisation (IVF), or other assisted reproductive technologies (ART)⁴³⁻⁴⁶. Frequently used medications include clomiphene citrate (CC), human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), human menopausal gonadotropin (hMG), gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), GnRH analogues, bromocriptine, and cabergoline⁴⁷⁻⁵³. However, these treatments may cause numerous adverse physical and psychological effects, such as breast tenderness, skin rash, nausea, vomiting, headaches, bloating, mood swings, depression, loss of bone density, among others^{54,55}. In addition, IVF treatment can be emotionally and financially burdensome for patients⁵⁶.

2.2. Male Infertility

Multiple factors can contribute to male infertility, including biological, behavioural, and lifestyle aspects, exposure to environmental elements, and sociodemographic variables⁵⁷.

Biological factors include genetic conditions, urogenital infections, and varicoceles.

Behavioural risk factors involve smoking, alcohol consumption, inadequate body mass index (BMI), sexual behaviour, and drug use. Environmental risks include exposure to chemicals, pesticides, and mycotoxins. Moreover, Sociodemographic risks include advanced age, which is significantly associated with male infertility⁵⁷.

However, according to Aston *et al.*⁵⁸, the cause of male infertility remains unknown in a considerable portion of patients.

The underdiagnosis of male infertility can have serious consequences, including increased burden on women and potential neglect of associated health conditions ranging from cardiovascular and autoimmune disorders to cancer and even mortality⁵⁹.

In this context, medical consultation is essential, allowing for appropriate diagnosis and treatment. Treatments may involve pharmacological interventions, surgical procedures, or ART⁶⁰. Nonetheless, therapeutic approaches have limitations, including low live birth rates, high costs, lengthy treatment cycles, and potential adverse reactions, among others⁶¹⁻⁶⁶.

3. Fertility and Infertility in the Perspective of Traditional Chinese Medicine

TCM has thousands of years of history in the treatment of infertility⁶⁷. TCM employs methods such as syndrome differentiation, overall conditioning, and multidirectional treatment strategies that promote fertility by addressing clinical symptoms as well as preventing and controlling the progression of infertility⁶⁷.

According to Ried *et al.*³⁸, several syndromes are recognised in TCM as contributors to female infertility, including deficiencies of Kidney *Jing*, Kidney *Yin*, or Kidney *Yang*, as well as Spleen deficiency, Blood deficiency, Liver *Qi* stagnation, blood stasis, and imbalances of Heat, Cold, or Dampness. These underlying disharmonies can be identified by observing menstrual cycle characteristics, combined with pulse and tongue diagnosis, and an assessment of physical and emotional well-being. Menstrual cycle quality is assessed by considering the appearance (colour, clots) and flow of menstrual blood, basal body temperature patterns, and the duration and regularity of the menstrual cycle. Adapted from Ried *et al.*³⁸, Table 1 presents the various syndromes observed in TCM clinical practice and their Western counterpart.

Table 1. Common syndromes associated with female infertility, adapted from Ried *et al.*³⁸.

Syndrome	Conventional Medicine Condition(s)
Kidney <i>Jing</i> Deficiency	Resistant ovarian syndrome, ovarian failure, advanced ovarian age, amenorrhea
Kidney <i>Yin</i> Deficiency	PMS, amenorrhea, mild PCOS, early menopause
Kidney <i>Yang</i> Deficiency	Amenorrhea, insufficient progesterone
Spleen <i>Qi</i> Deficiency	Amenorrhea, fibroids
Blood Deficiency	Dysmenorrhea, amenorrhea, PCOS
Liver <i>Qi</i> Stagnation	PMS, dysmenorrhea, irregular menstruation, and amenorrhea
Heat, Kidney <i>Yin</i> Deficiency	May be associated with hyperactive thyroid, essential hypertension, and menopausal symptoms
Liver or Heart Fire	Metrorrhagia/mid-cycle bleeding, PMS
Damp-Heat	Infection, inflammation, endometritis, PID
Phlegm-Damp or Cold-Damp	Fallopian tube blockage, PCOS, ovarian cysts, amenorrhea, dysmenorrhea
Blood Stasis and Dampness	Endometriosis, ovarian cysts, fibroids
Cold Uterus	Recurrent miscarriage

For the full table containing data regarding basal body temperature, menstrual quality, tongue, pulse, and other symptoms, please refer to the work of Ried *et al.*³⁸.

Concerning male infertility, Zhijie *et al.*⁶⁸ reported that it is often characterised by combinations of multiple underlying syndromes rather than a single issue. Their scientific analysis identified several key TCM syndromes commonly observed, summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Common syndromes associated with male infertility according to Zhijie et al. ⁶⁸.

Kidney	Yang Deficiency Qi Deficiency
Spleen	Yang Deficiency
Liver	Qi Stagnation
Qi Stagnation with Blood Stasis	
Damp-Heat	

The study highlighted that most men did not present only a single syndrome, but rather complex combinations of syndromes. The most common complex pattern was a combination of Spleen-Kidney Yang deficiency with Liver Qi stagnation.

4. Scientific Evidence on Herbal Medicine for Fertility

The use of plants for health is considered an ancient practice developed over centuries ^{69,70}. Herbal medicine continues to be widely used today and has influenced modern medical practice ^{71,72}.

Chinese herbal medicine incorporates not only plants but also minerals and animal-derived materials in its formulations.

Given its systematic use throughout China's history and its apparent empirical efficacy, it is essential to investigate scientifically its effectiveness, composition, and mechanisms of action.

4.1. Herbal Medicine for Female Fertility

In a study by Aguiar *et al.* ¹², a systematic review of recent and methodologically rigorous randomised controlled trials was conducted.

This review identified relevant formulas for treating female infertility. The two most frequently studied formulas were *Zishen Yutai* and *Dingkun*. Table 3 provides further details on these formulas.

Table 3. Most recently studied formulas, compositions, and mechanisms according to the study of Aguiar *et al.* ¹².

Formula	Composition	Mechanisms
Zishen Yutai	<i>Cuscuta sinensis Lam., Fructus Amomi, Radix Rehmanniae Preparata, Ginseng, Herba Taxilli, Colla Corii Asini, Polygonum multiflorum, Artemisiae argyi folium, Morinda officinalis, Atractylodes macrocephala, Codonopsis radix, Cornu Cervi degelatinatum, Fructus Lycii, Dipsaci radix, Eucommia ulmoides.</i>	Improves endometrial receptivity by upregulating HOXA10, increasing ITGβ3, and decreasing EMX2; modulates microRNAs (miR-135a, miR-196b); enhances ovarian reserve by regulating hormones (E2, P, FSH, LH) and receptors (FSHR, LHR); modulates angiogenesis via VEGF and sVEGFR-1.
Dingkun	<i>Ginseng, Cornu Cervi pantotrichum, Radix Angelicae sinensis, Radix Rehmanniae preparata, Stigma croci, Caulis Spatholobi, Radix Notoginseng, Radix Paeoniae alba, Rhizoma Atractylodis macrocephalae, Fructus Lycii, Radix Scutellariae, Rhizoma Cyperi, Fructus Leonuri, Rhizoma Ligustici Chuanxiong, Cornu Cervi degelatinatum, Colla Corii Asini, Rhizoma Corydalis, Flos Carthami, Herba Leonuri, Faeces Togopteri, Poria, Radix Bupleuri, Radix Linderae, Fructus Amomi villosi, Cortex Eucommiae, Rhizoma Zingiberis, Herba Asari, Radix Cyathulae, Cortex Cinnamomi, Radix Glycyrrhizae.</i>	Estrogenic effects via activation of ERα and ERβ; improves endometrial receptivity through modulation of HB-EGF, crucial for uterine-embryo communication during implantation.

Specifically, *Zishen Yutai* Formula demonstrated positive effects on fertility, including higher rates of clinical pregnancy and live births compared to placebo, suggesting benefits for fetal development. It also improved embryo implantation rates, although spontaneous abortion rates did not significantly differ between treatment and placebo groups. From the TCM perspective, *Zishen* means “tonify the Kidney”, and *Yutai* means “nourish the fetus.” Developed by Professor Yuankai Luo, it is prescribed for threatened or recurrent miscarriage, aiming to tonify the Kidney and strengthen *Yuan Qi* ^{73,74}.

Regarding *Dingkun* Formula, the studies analysed by Aguiar *et al.* ¹² also suggest beneficial effects, particularly in specific subgroups. *Dingkun* was linked to a greater number of high-quality blastocysts, indicating potential improvement in embryonic development. In women under 37, supplementation with *Dingkun* resulted in significantly higher ongoing pregnancy rates compared with placebo. It also improved cumulative pregnancy rates when combined with hormonal therapy in women with a thin endometrium. Historically, *Dingkun* was developed during the reign of Emperor Qianlong of the *Qing* Dynasty (1636–1912 CE) as an “imperial harem sacred medicine,” used exclusively in the royal court ⁷⁵. In TCM, *Dingkun* is used to tonify the Liver and Kidney, invigorate *Qi*, nourish the blood, regulate menstruation, relieve depression, promote blood circulation, and alleviate pain ⁷⁵.

However, other studies also support herbal medicine as crucial in infertility treatment. For instance, Deng *et al.* ⁷⁶ found that the combination of TCM techniques with herbal medicine (e.g., moxibustion + herbal medicine, fire-needle acupuncture + herbal medicine, etc.) improved clinical pregnancy and ovulation rates in women with infertility related to Polycystic Ovary Syndrome when compared with the use of single therapies such as acupuncture, herbal medicine, or Western medicine alone. Specifically, moxibustion plus herbal medicine, fire-needle acupuncture plus herbal medicine, and acupuncture plus herbal medicine were more effective for achieving pregnancy, while fire-needle acupuncture plus herbal medicine, acupuncture plus herbal medicine, and auricular acupressure combined with herbal enema plus herbal medicine were the most effective for inducing ovulation.

Similarly, the meta-analysis by Hyun *et al.* ⁷⁷ showed that Chinese herbal medicine combined with other treatments is more effective compared to these other treatments when applied individually (including conventional medical interventions). These authors also noted that Chinese herbal medicine can improve pregnancy rates, which are significantly higher when compared with placebo, and that it may be more effective or at least equally effective when compared with other therapeutic interventions.

4.2. Herbal Medicine for Male Fertility

A recent meta-analysis ⁷⁸, indicates that plant-based remedies promote spermatogenesis by optimising semen parameters, sex hormone levels, and antioxidant profiles. The Chinese formulas analysed included *Shao-Fu-Zhu-Yu-Tang* and a *new herbal combination* developed for male infertility. Their compositions are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Composition of Chinese Formulas for Male Infertility analysed in the study of Nguyen-Thanh *et al.* ⁷⁸.

<i>Shao-Fu-Zhu-Yu-Tang</i>	“New formula” ⁷⁹
<i>Angelica sinensis</i> , <i>Ligusticum chuanxiong</i> , <i>Paeonia veitchii</i> , <i>Trogopterus xanthipes</i> , <i>Typha angustata</i> , <i>Commiphora molmol</i> , <i>Corydalis yanhusuo</i> , <i>Zingiber officinale</i> , <i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> , <i>Foeniculum vulgare</i> .	<i>Chlorophytum borivillianum</i> , <i>Hygrophila spinosa</i> , <i>Mucuna pruriens</i> , <i>Mimosa pudica</i> , <i>Acacia senegal</i> , <i>Astragalus membranaceus</i> , <i>Plantago ovata</i> , <i>Bombax ceiba</i> , <i>Eurycoma longifolia</i> , Rock candy.

The *Shao-Fu-Zhu-Yu-Tang* formula, studied by Yang *et al.* ⁸⁰, appears to be capable not only of increasing sperm motility *in vitro* (in a laboratory environment) but also of improving sperm motility, increasing the number of sperm with normal morphology, and enhancing semen quality *in vivo* (within the organism). The researchers also suggest that the positive effects of the formula may be due to its ability to increase acrosin activity (an

enzyme crucial for the sperm's capacity to penetrate the ovum), reduce free radicals (acting as an antioxidant), and improve the environment of the seminal fluid. According to the principles of TCM, the *Shao-Fu-Zhu-Yu-Tang* formula (*Shao Fu* meaning "lower burner" and *Zhu Yu* "remover of stasis") is used for the treatment of Blood stasis^{80,81}. Originally described in the monograph "*Correction of Errors in Medical Classics*" compiled by Qingren Wang in the *Qing* Dynasty, it is considered a classical prescription and valid for the treatment of pathologies caused by stagnation due to Cold and Blood stasis⁸¹.

On the other hand, the "*New Polyherbal Formula*"⁷⁹ was able to significantly improve semen quantity and quality in adult men with oligospermia (low sperm count) when compared with a placebo. In addition, it also improved serum levels of testosterone, luteinizing hormone, and follicle-stimulating hormone in most treated men compared with placebo. These results suggest that this formulation may represent a new and promising therapeutic combination that can be used to enhance the spermatogenic potential of many infertile men with oligospermia. The authors further suggest that this spermatogenic potential may be due to the possible synergistic action of the selected herbal components used in the preparation.

However, as Fang *et al.*⁸² point out, other formulas are also used for the treatment of male infertility. For example, *Wuzi Yanzong* is a five-herb formula used for centuries, with numerous clinical studies supporting its efficacy in improving sperm density and overall semen quality^{83,84}. Randomised clinical trials have shown positive results compared with treatment with vitamin C/E and placebo, with improvements in sperm concentration, motility, and even higher pregnancy rates in partners⁸⁵⁻⁸⁸. According to Yong *et al.*⁸⁹, *Wuzi Yanzong* is the most commonly prescribed Chinese herbal medicine for the treatment of male infertility. This prescription is known as "*The first ancient and modern prescription for the treatment of infertility*", having first been documented in *She Sheng Zhong Miao Fang*, edited by Shi-che Zhang in the *Ming* Dynasty^{89,90}. Its purpose is to nourish the Kidney and *Jing*^{89,91,92}.

Another example is the *Zuogui* formula, a classical prescription designed to tonify the Kidney, also used for male infertility⁸². One study demonstrated a high rate of clinical efficacy⁹³, with improvements in semen quality and increased levels of testosterone and luteinizing hormone. It is particularly noted for improving sperm density in oligospermia and sperm motility in asthenozoospermia (low sperm motility). *Zuogui* is also a commonly used formula, created by Zhang Jingyue, as described in *Jingyue Quanshu* ("*Complete Works of Jingyue*") in 1624⁹⁴. According to the theory of TCM, it is indicated for Kidney *Yin* deficiency syndrome⁹⁵, which, according to Lian *et al.*⁹⁶, manifests as dysphoria with feverish sensation in the chest, palms, and soles, hot flashes, night sweats, pain in the waist and knees, and dry mouth. This formula is also often used in China for the treatment of osteoporosis⁹⁷.

Additionally, *Qilin* is a complex traditional Chinese formula focused on tonifying the Kidney, replenishing *Jing*, supplementing *Qi*, and nourishing the *Xue*^{82,98}. Studies, including a multicenter, randomised, controlled clinical trial⁹⁸, have demonstrated significant improvements in sperm motility, total sperm count, and progressively motile sperm. This formula is also considered compatible with other medications for male infertility⁹⁹⁻¹⁰².

Another ancient traditional Chinese formula, *Jinkui Shenqi*, has been applied for the treatment of patients with Kidney *Yang* deficiency syndrome for about 2000 years in China⁸². Recent studies have shown that it has satisfactory therapeutic effects in male infertility caused by oligoasthenozoospermia, with significant improvements in semen quality after treatment¹⁰³. This formula was first recorded in the ancient classic *Jin Gui Yao Lue* (*Essentials from the Golden Cabinet*) and is still widely used today¹⁰⁴.

Finally, mention should also be made of the *Zhibai Dihuang* Decoction. This is generally used for hyperactive Fire due to *Yin* deficiency⁸². Studies have shown that it has protective effects in male infertility, restoring semen quality indicators such as liquefaction time, motility rate, and survival rate¹⁰⁵. This formula was first included in the *Jingyue Quanshu* by Jingyue Zhang (1563–1640), where it is indicated for the treatment of Kidney

deficiency ¹⁰⁶, with the function of nourishing *Yin* and the Kidney, removing Heat, and reducing Fire ¹⁰⁷.

5. Final Remarks

This study explored the complex interaction between fertility and infertility, describing the perspective of TCM on these conditions and presenting a review of the scientific evidence regarding the application of Chinese herbal medicine in the field of fertility.

Infertility, a global health problem with significant impact on individuals, families, and society, requires comprehensive and effective therapeutic approaches. The limitations of conventional treatments, including adverse effects and high costs, highlight the need to explore complementary therapies, such as Chinese herbal medicine.

In this context, the advancement of scientific knowledge about traditional therapeutic approaches has gained recognition for its potential contribution to global health ¹⁰⁸. Adapting these traditional techniques to contemporary healthcare contexts may offer an effective and economical solution to the modern challenges of healthcare ^{35,109,110}.

Furthermore, their complementary potential to conventional techniques is promising within the broad concept of integrative medicine ¹¹¹⁻¹¹⁶.

Specifically, the scientific evidence presented in this study reveals the promising potential of Chinese herbal medicine in the treatment of infertility, both female and male. Several herbal formulas have demonstrated positive effects on improving semen quality, sperm motility, pregnancy rates, and other parameters relevant to fertility.

The mechanisms of action of these formulas are complex, involving the modulation of signalling pathways, hormonal regulation, improvement of endometrial receptivity, and protection against oxidative stress, among other biological processes. However, it is important to emphasise that scientific research in this area is still under development, and many studies lack greater methodological rigour and larger sample sizes to confirm the results and elucidate the mechanisms of action with greater precision.

6. Conclusions

The findings of this study indicate that Chinese herbal medicine holds considerable potential as a complementary strategy in the management of infertility. By addressing both male and female reproductive disorders, herbal formulations offer therapeutic benefits that extend beyond those provided by conventional treatments, improving semen parameters, sperm motility, pregnancy rates, and overall reproductive health.

Nevertheless, it is essential to recognise that current evidence, while promising, is still evolving. Future research should prioritise high-quality, large-scale randomised controlled trials to validate these preliminary findings, clarify mechanisms of action, and establish standardised protocols for safe and effective clinical application.

In conclusion, Chinese herbal medicine represents a valuable therapeutic resource that, with further scientific validation, may play a significant role in advancing reproductive healthcare and improving outcomes for patients experiencing infertility.

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